

THE DEMOGRAPHIC DYNAMICS AND DISTRIBUTION OF THE POPULATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The area of Uzbekistan's territory is 448.9 thousand km². Its population exceeds 37.5 million people, with 86.6 people per 1 km². Among the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), Uzbekistan ranks third in terms of population, after Russia and Ukraine. The capital city, Tashkent, is part of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which also includes the Republic of Karakalpakstan and 12 provinces.*

Keywords: *population, labor resources, dynamics, men, women, youth, urban and rural population distribution.*

It is important to suggest that the population of any country is the source of its labor resources. Only the working-age population is considered part of the labor resources. In Uzbekistan, the labor resources are considered to be males aged 16 to 59 and females aged 16 to 54. In the territories of Uzbekistan, during the second half of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, the birth rate was very high. The number of births per thousand people per year ranged from 45 to 55. 80% of the population lived in rural areas. During that time, the average life expectancy was 32 years, but by 1989-1990, it had increased to 69.3 years, and by 2010-2011, it had reached 72.7 years. The life expectancy for women during this period increased from 72.4 years to 74.9 years, while for men it rose from 66.1 years to 70.6 years.

It is worth mentioning that as of January 1, 2025 the permanent population of Uzbekistan reached 37,543.2 thousand people. Thus, in 2024, the population growth was 2%, or 743.4 thousand people. According to the statistics agency, the total population consists of 18.9 million men (50.4%) and 18.6 million women (49.6%). The urban population is 19.1 million (51%), while the rural population is 18.4 million (49%).

Certainly, in terms of regional population density, the highest density is found in Tashkent city with 6,948.1 people per square kilometer, followed by Andijan region with 804.9, and Fergana region with 613.1 people per square kilometer. The lowest densities are observed in Navoi region (9.9) and Karakalpakstan (12.2).

Definitely, in 2024, 926.4 thousand babies were born, which is 3.7% fewer than the previous year. The fathers of newborns were distributed by age as follows: 10.7% were under 25

years old, 82.5% were between 25-39 years old, and 6.8% were 40 years old or older. The mothers of newborns were distributed as follows: 39.3% were under 25 years old, 59.5% were between 25-39 years old, and 1.2% were 40 years old or older. The highest birth rates were observed in Samarkand region (12%), Fergana region (11.1%), Kashkadarya region (10.9%), Andijan region (9.3%), and Surkhandarya region (9.1%). The lowest birth rates were in Syrdarya region (2.4%), Navoi region (2.8%), Jizzakh region (4.2%), Karakalpakstan (4.5%) and Bukhara region (5%).

According to the statistics agency, the number of marriages registered in 2024 was 271.8 thousand, which is 12 thousand fewer than the previous year. The average age of women at marriage was 22.3 years and the average age of men was 27.1 years. The number of divorces was 45.1 thousand, which is 8.3% less than in 2023. The average age of divorced men was 35.4 years, and the average age of divorced women was 32.1 years. The largest proportion of divorces occurred among women under 35, accounting for 64.6% of the total.

In 2024, 2,229 people immigrated to Uzbekistan from abroad, while 10,842 people emigrated.

As of January 1, 2025, the average population density in Uzbekistan is 86.6 people per square kilometer. This is an increase of 1.6 people compared to the same period last year. The highest population densities by region are in Tashkent city (6,948.1 people per square kilometer), Andijan region (804.9 people), and Fergana region (613.1 people). Population density per square kilometer in various regions is as follows: Republic of Karakalpakstan- 12.2 people, Andijan region- 804.9 people, Bukhara region - 51.6 people, Jizzakh region - 72.5 people, Kashkadarya region- 127.4 people, Navoi region- 9.9 people, Namangan region- 420.9 people, Samarkand region- 256.3 people, Surkhandarya region-146.5 people, Syrdarya region- 217.5 people, Tashkent region- 205.3 people, Fergana region- 613.1 people, Khorezm region- 335.9 people and Tashkent city- 6,948.1 people.

Figure 1. Population Dynamics

The top ten districts and cities with the highest population in Uzbekistan have been identified. The ten districts and cities with the highest population are as follows:

Figure 2. Cities and Districts with the Highest Population in Uzbekistan

As of January 1, 2025, the following cities and districts have the highest population: Namangan city - 713.4 thousand people, Samarkand city - 595.8 thousand people, Urgut district - 572.6 thousand people, Andijan city- 492.4 thousand people, Denov district - 430.5 thousand people, Olmazar district- 412.0 thousand people, Past Dargom district - 392.1 thousand people, Yunusabad district - 385.2 thousand people, Shayhontohur district - 369.9 thousand people, Asaka district- 362.1 thousand people.

As of February 9, 2025 the Statistics Agency has also published the list of the ten cities and districts with the lowest population. These are: Gozgon city - 9.3 thousand people, Tomdi district - 15.3 thousand people, Shirin city - 19.4 thousand people, Korovulbazar district – 20.3 thousand people, Bozatov district - 21.9 thousand people, Yangiobod district – 30.2 thousand people, Moynok district - 33.9 thousand people, Konimekh district - 37.2 thousand people, Takhtakupir district - 38.9 thousand people, Uchkuduk district - 39.7 thousand people. (Figure 3)

Figure 3. Cities and Districts with the Lowest Population in Uzbekistan

According to the data from the Statistics Agency, in 2024, a total of 21,107 cases of twin births were recorded by the civil registry offices. Among them, 10,630 were male children and 10,477 were female children. In January and December of 2024, based on the age of the fathers of the newborns, 10.7% of the newborns' fathers were under 25 years old, 82.5% were between 25-39 years old, and 6.8% of the fathers were 40 years or older.

By summarizing it should be suggested that the growth in population is being reported through international channels and by the State Statistics Agency, with information provided through the Uzbekistan National Information Agency's platforms.

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